

Event Abstract

Assessing Interactions Between Periodontal Pathogens, Human Oral Cell Lines and Probiotics

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Background: Probiotics are live micro-organisms which, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host. Probiotic research has become a hot topic in medicine. As in other fields of healthcare and have been introduced for prevention and treatment of periodontal diseases. Few studies have evaluated the possible benefits of adding probiotics to infected oral tissues with periodontal pathogens. **Method:** We have investigated weather probiotics species namely, *L. rhamnosus* GG ATCC 53103, *L. reuteri* ATCC 55730 and *S. salivarius* K-12 can inhibit *F. nucleatum* ATCC 10953, *P. gingivalis* ATCC 33277 and *A. actinomycetemcomitans* ATCC 33384 respectively of HOKs and GSM-K cells in culture. **Results:** When both cell lines were exposed to *F. nucleatum*, *P. gingivalis* and *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, (13.1%, 21.12% and 50.90%) of GSM-K respectively and (34.75%, 40.78% and 51.97%) of HOKs respectively remained viable after 24hr incubation. However, in the presence of 10⁸ CFU/ml of live different probiotics species tested, the viability of the infected GSM-K cells exposed to *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG increased for *F. nucleatum*, *P. gingivalis* and *A. actinomycetemcomitans* to 69.34 (p=0.00018), 64.05% (p<0.001) and 66.74 (p<0.05) respectively and for HOKs viability increased to 69.82% (p=0.000097), 75.45% (p=0.00018) and 90.38% (p=0.0023). *L. reuteri* addition increase viability of GSM-K infected by *F. nucleatum*, *P. gingivalis* and *A. actinomycetemcomitans* to 72.86% (p=0.0046), 58.46% (p=0.0096) and 71.73% (p=0.05) respectively and HOKs viability infected by same pathogens to 74.65% (p=0.0001), 77.08% (p=0.0005) and 67.31% (p=0.067) respectively. *S. salivarius* increases viability of GSM-K cells to 61.33% (p=0.015), 65.51% (p=0.0029) and 67.84% (p=0.035). For HOKs 81.67% (p=0.001), 81.7% (p=0.00079) and 55.71% (p=0.44) respectively following the same order above for infection with pathogens.

Furthermore, live bacteria, lysate or spent culture fluid all protect both cell lines infected by tested pathogens apart from addition of *S. salivarius* spent culture fluid to *A. actinomycetemcomitans* infected GSM-K cells (p=0.46) and *S. salivarius* both bacterial suspension (p=0.44) and lysate (p=0.14) to *A. actinomycetemcomitans* infected HOKs cells. **Conclusion:** These results suggest that probiotics can be used in oral products to protect against oral periodontal pathogens toxicity.

Keywords: Periodontal, Pathogens, Probiotics.

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